

Uterine Leiomyomas Management from the Present to the Future

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Abstract

Previous studies showed to manage of uterine leiomyomas but in the diagnosis, part analysing they showed result to manage the uterine leiomyomas and surgical treatments. Hence, we are looking for alternative to early diagnosis by using the advance technology to manage and reduce surgical operation. These tumors are most prevalent during the reproductive years and regress after menopause. In white women, the incidence of leiomyomas is thought to be 43% by age 35 years and almost 59% by age 50 years. The average treatment duration was 3 to 6 months. The many of the trials reported fibroid volume and area of the uterus with a greater decrease in the fibroid volume.

Keywords: uterine leiomyomas, uterus, fibronectin, extracellular matrix and hormones

I. Introduction

Uterine leiomyomas, the group of cells forms tissue and muscles in the body generally uterine is a part of a female reproduction system where fetus is grown that is attached to the placenta. The female sex hormones are estrogen and progesterone. They help in regulate and development of egg where it is in ovary. Female has normal menstrual cycle and this is controlled hormones that these glands produce. After 28 days cycle endometrium lining is shedding or breaks down and blood is released and is a sign that pregnancy has not occurred. At the age of 30 to 50 of reproductive women arise with the most gynecologic tumors i.e., uterine leiomyomas are a benign tumor of the smooth muscle cells of the uterus. Which arise in and around uterus under the influence of growth factors and sex hormones such as estrogen & progesterone [1]. Uterine leiomyomas are also called as fibroids and fibromyomas can be asymptomatic or may be symptomatic they occur in different location within uterus such as intramural, pedunculated, sub serosal, submucosal etc. These tumors are most prevalent during the reproductive years and regress after menopause. In white women, the incidence of leiomyomas is thought to be 43% by age 35 years and almost 59% by age 50 years [2]. The incidence is even higher among African – American women at 59% by age 35 years and more than 75% by age 50 years. An estimated 3-5 billion dollars is spent annually in the America for the diagnosis and making management of myomas. Occurring in nearly 70% of all reproductive aged women the indication for hysterectomy worldwide. [3]

Fig.1 Schematic showing location of uterine leiomyoma within uterus (2).

II. Etiology/ Cause

The cause of fibrosis is unknown each tumor's is of monoclonal origin and involved include the sex steroid hormones estrogen and progesterone and even the insulin like growth factors, epidermal and transforming growth factor. The primary mechanism by which fibroids may causes subfertility is unknown however they are thought to be estrogen and progesterone dependent because fibroid as are known to shrink after either menopause [2] Extra cellular matrix (ECM) accumulation is expected to be dangerous leiomyomas diseases that is uterine leiomyoma. ECM which functions like an accumulation of the lump structure of fibroids, and the ECM- rich rigid structure within tumors is considered to the cause of abnormal and heavy bleeding and pelvic pain. Therefore, ECM accumulation and it is dangerous for developing new drug molecule for uterine leiomyomas. We discuss the basis of ECM in leiomyomas and the role of ECM as reservoir for growth factors and a modulator of their action. The components of ECM – collagens, fibronectin, laminins, fibulin-3, proteoglycans, MMP's TIMP's, activin -A and other cytokines [4].

Fig.2 Diagram of uterus shows different between healthy uterus and diseased uterus.

Fig.3 mechanism of Regulation of extracellular matrix by growth factors and hormones in uterine leiomyoma.

III. Risk factors Associated with Leiomyoma's

Risk factors for uterine leiomyomas may achieve significance through their contribution to either the initiation or promotion phases of tumorigenesis. Although their impact often appears related to their effect upon oestrogen and progesterone, other mechanisms may be involved. For example, early menarche increases the overall oestrogen exposure, but also involves more menstruations with their concomitant tissue damage. Two of the more consistent risk factors that have been identified are age (late reproductive years) and African-American ethnicity. The effect of age may reflect more opportunity for dysregulated cells to be produced or, alternatively, a prolonged period for growth under the hormonal influences of the reproductive years. Why African-American women are at higher risk for clinically significant fibroids is not known, but apparent metabolic differences could increase the estrogenic promotional effect, such as the predilection for the 16α hydroxylation of oestradiol metabolic pathway. Increased risk has also been related with early menarche, nulliparity, and obesity, whereas decreased risk has been found with increasing parity and smoking. On the basis study of clinical reports, tamoxifen also appears to be a risk factor. Finally, the most important piece of the fibroid puzzle, the initiator remains unsolved. Uterine leiomyomas Symptom which includes abnormal menstrual bleeding, pelvic pain, dysmenorrhea, infertility and recurrent pregnancy loss [5]

Fig.4 location of fibroids presents in uterus

iv. Treatment/Diagnosis

1. *Pharmacological Treatments*: Surgery to improve intraoperative and postoperative outcomes such therapies tend to be expensive. Fibroids have unacceptable side effects long term. Other potential hormonal treatment, include progestin and selective progesterone-receptor modulators (SPRM). Uterine artery embolization (UAE) is a non-invasive alternative to open surgery in the treatment of uterine myxomatosis. It is a safety procedure with decrease of complication for treatment of uterine leiomyomata. Acupuncture is an ancient Chinese method which has been used for both the management and diagnosis the disease for over 3000years there are many types of acupuncture used to manage uterine leiomyomas [8]. Herbal preparation used within the included trials. The average treatment duration was 3to 6 months. The many of the trials reported fibroid volume and area of the uterus with a greater decrease in the fibroid volume. Updated treatment or a surgery is robotic surgery for the tumour gynaecological disease [7]. Hysteroscopic resection: this procedure is appropriate for submucosal leiomyomas, and it can allow many patients to avoid hysterectomy.

Si.No.	Medical management	interventional radiology	surgical management
2	NSAIDs	UAE	Hysterectomy
3	Tranexamic acid	MRgFUS	Myomectomy
4	Combined contraceptives	--	Laparoscopic
5	progestins	--	robotic
6	GnRH agonists and antagonists	--	--
7	Anti-progestins etc	--	--

Myomectomy this surgical removal of only the leiomyoma is most commonly offered to women who like to preserve the ability to have children.

Hysterectomy the only definitive treatment, hysterectomy is appropriate for women who do not wish have children. It can be performed by several different routes by laparotomy or with use of a robotic surgical system [6].

Other therapeutic option such as drugs used for ulsis mifepristone treatment showed that moderate effect in relief of bleeding and showed an improvement in fibroid specific quality of life. Tripterygium, wilfordil and anti progestin and natural compounds have been showed as effective treatments that targets ECM in uterine leiomyomas leuprolide acetate, cetorelix acetate, asoprisnil, ulipristal, raloxifene, curcumin, liarozole, all trans retinoic acid, vitamin D, tranilast, pifrenidone, halofuginone [9].

2. *Non-Pharmacological Treatment:* Life style choices which have a significant impact on risk of UL development.

Improve the lack of exercise, intake of green vegetables diets and maintaining the balance of body mass index (BMI) can prevent, treat or reduce the increase of uterine leiomyomas incidence. The main cause of uterine disease is stress which is caused by work load and less sleeping etc. also maintain the hormonal balanced level in the body and this reduces upcoming tumours in uterine [6] .

V. CONCLUSION

Uterine leiomyomas are associated with significant morbidity and can have a devastating impact on quality of life among women during their reproductive years. Since ECM is involved in both pathological and physiological processes, it will be an important challenge to identify compounds that specifically target unwanted fibrosis and optimize their use in interrupting the fibrotic process without disturbing the normal physiological environment. Other changes in modern lifestyle, such as dietary shifts to a higher-fat, lower-fibre diet and the potential impact of environmental oestrogens, could also be significant because of increased oestrogen exposure. Previous studies showed to manage of uterine leiomyomas but in the diagnosis, part analysing they showed result to manage the uterine leiomyomas and surgical treatments. Hence, we are looking for alternative to early diagnosis by using the advance technology to manage and reduce surgical operation. Interestingly some of research article has been report new advance technology for the laser operation a dearly management by using home remedies.

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